

COST-EFFECTIVENESS OF STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING ON THE LIFECYCLE OF COMPOSITE AEROSPACE ELEMENTS

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Keywords: mechanical testing; process monitoring; autoclave; cure; damage tolerance

ABSTRACT

Structural Health Monitoring Systems (SHMS) enable real-time monitoring of composite aeronautical structures, offering the potential to reduce maintenance efforts. However, their overall impact on the lifecycle remains uncertain. This study presents a methodology to assess the economic impact of SHMS, structured in four steps: (i) identification of SHMS applications, (ii) assessment of SHMS performance, (iii) integration of SHMS into the lifecycle, (iv) evaluation of the resulting economic impact. The methodology is applied to two distinct lifecycle stages of a composite rotorcraft blade: the Beginning of Life (BOL), which involves the development of a new sensorized component, and the Middle of Life (MOL), which focuses on its operational use and maintenance. In the BOL phase, results indicate that SHMS can offer economic advantages if they enable a reduction in the number of curing cycles below a certain threshold. In the MOL phase, while SHMS reduce manpower needs, these savings are offset by higher spare parts costs and longer repair times. The findings highlight the importance of considering both technical performance and cost implications when integrating SHMS into aerospace applications.

NOMENCLATURE

... ^{as is}	Superscript referring to the scenario “as is”
... ^{SHMS}	Superscript referring to the scenario “with SHMS”
$C_{acq\ sys}$	Cost of the acquisition system for the scenario “as is”
c_{blade}	Cost of the blade to the customer
$C_{cur\ cycle\ def}$	Cost to define the curing cycle
C_{energy}	Cost of energy for the autoclave
CF	Cash flow per year
C_{FBG}	Cost of 1 FBG sensor
$C_{FBG\ sys}$	Cost of the interrogation system for FBG sensors
c_{fuel}	Cost of fuel per hour consumed by the helicopter
C_g	Cost of 1 strain gauge
$C_{lab\ act}$	Cost to perform laboratory activities
C_m	Cost of the material to produce one blade

$C_{test\ lab}$	Cost to perform laboratory tests
C_{th}	Cost of 1 thermocouple
$K_{partition}$	Partition coefficient
L_{eng}	Labour rate of engineers
L_{pilots}	Labour rate of pilots
$L_{tr\ wo}$	Labour rate of trained workers
n_{auto}	Number of autoclave cycles
n_b	Number of rotor blades
n_{FBG}	Number of FBG sensors embedded in one blade
n_g	Number of strain gauges applied on one blade
n_{test}	Number of laboratory blade tests
n_{th}	Number of thermocouples embedded in one blade
R	Revenue loss
r	Discount rate
t_{auto}	Time to perform one autoclave cycle
t_{depot}	Time needed by the helicopter to reach the depot
t_{DI}	Time to perform detailed inspection
t_{eng}	Time needed by the engineers to assess the quality of the acquired data
t_{GVI}	Time to perform general visual inspection
$t_{mount\ blade}$	Time to mount one blade on the rotor hub
t_{repair}	Time to repair one blade
t_{test}	Time to perform one test on the blade
$t_{tr\ wo}$	Time needed by the trained workers to laminate, prepare the vacuum bag and demould the blade

1 INTRODUCTION

Maintenance is a critical activity for ensuring safety in the aviation sector; however, it requires substantial resources in terms of manpower, spare parts, and downtime. In commercial aviation, maintenance can represent up to 28% of total operational costs [1]. At present, maintenance activities rely on Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) techniques such as tapping, ultrasound, and radiography. While these methods are effective, they are restricted to localized inspections, must be performed while the aircraft is on the ground, and often necessitate disassembly of components for access. In comparison, Structural Health Monitoring Systems (SHMS) offer continuous, in-situ monitoring capabilities and allow for the inspection of larger areas than conventional NDT. The use of SHMS in aerospace structures has been extensively explored. For instance, [2] evaluated the performance of a fiber Bragg grating (FBG)-based SHMS on a stiffened metallic helicopter panel under different crack lengths. In [3], a strain-based SHMS was employed to detect damage in a helicopter rotor blade, while [4] used convolutional neural networks to identify damage in composite wings. Although these studies demonstrate clear benefits—particularly in improving safety and enabling condition-based maintenance—the economic impact of SHMS over the lifecycle of monitored structures remains uncertain. In [1], the deployment of Piezoelectric Wafer Active Sensors on a commercial aircraft fuselage was found to offer no economic advantage, as maintenance savings were offset by increased fuel consumption from the added SHMS weight. In [5], replacing A-check and C-check inspections with piezoelectric sensors affected aircraft performance, making SHMS economically impractical. Conversely, [6] indicated potential cost savings when SHMS replaced DVI and GVI using ultrasonic and FBG sensors on an Airbus A320. In [7], SHMS enabled greater allowable design limits and mass reduction for damage-tolerant composite structures, though no benefits were observed for structures designed against instability. To date, most existing research has focused on fixed-wing aircraft [1, 5–10], and, to the best of the authors' knowledge, no studies have assessed the economic implications

of SHMS applied to helicopter structural elements. Moreover, current literature primarily addresses the operational phase, often overlooking the possible impacts of SHMS on the production and development stages.

This study evaluates the economic impact of an optical fiber-based SHMS applied to composite rotorcraft blades. The SHMS performance was assessed using a finite element model of the blade, allowing simulation of multiple damage scenarios used to train an artificial neural network (ANN)-based damage detection algorithm. Both the Beginning of Life (BOL)—which corresponds to production—and the Middle of Life (MOL)—which concerns usage—were examined. The IDEF0 formalism was used to define key processes, inputs, outputs, resources, and constraints, thus forming the foundation for the cost model. Two scenarios were compared using the Life Cycle Cost (LCC) methodology: the current configuration without SHMS (“as-is” scenario) and an alternative configuration with blades equipped with FBG sensors (“with SHMS”).

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the scenarios and associated cost models, including the methodology used to derive them across the BOL and MOL phases. Section 3 describes the cost model implementation, providing a parametric analysis for BOL and a Probabilistic Damage Tolerance Analysis for MOL. Section 4 concludes with the main findings of the study.

2 DEVELOPMENT OF THE COST MODEL

The lifecycle of any product can typically be divided into three main stages: (i) BOL, during which the component is manufactured and introduced to the market; (ii) MOL, during which the component is used and maintained by the customer to perform its intended operational functions; and (iii) End of Life (EOL), when the component is decommissioned and disposed of. This study focuses on the first two stages of the lifecycle: BOL and MOL. To evaluate the economic impact of SHMS on the rotorcraft lifecycle, the following methodology was adopted: (i) identification of the SHMS application; (ii) assessment of SHMS performance; (iii) integration of SHMS into the lifecycle; and (iv) evaluation of the economic impact. Based on this procedure, a composite rotorcraft blade instrumented with FBG sensors was selected as the reference structural element. The choice of FBG sensors is justified by their immunity to electromagnetic interference and their ability to be embedded within the composite laminate with minimal invasiveness [11].

The following subsections provide further details on each step of the proposed methodology.

2.1 Beginning Of Life

With regard to step (ii) of the procedure for assessing the economic impact of SHMS, the performance of the SHMS was not evaluated in this work, as doing so would have required an extensive experimental campaign. Instead, this section focuses on step (iii), which concerns the integration of SHMS into the rotorcraft lifecycle.

At the BOL stage, two applications of SHMS were considered in relation to the laboratory activities required for developing a new composite blade: the definition of the curing cycle and the execution of laboratory tests. The first application relates to the optimization of the curing cycle, in which the evolution of pressure and temperature over time is determined. The second involves laboratory testing to verify the structural integrity of the blade during the initial certification phase.

Currently, defining the appropriate curing cycle for composite elements requires several iterations, since the polymerization of thermoset composites is an exothermic process, and the internal temperature distribution often deviates from the one imposed by the autoclave. Temperature measurements are typically obtained by embedding thermocouples in the laminate, and the curing cycle is repeated and adjusted until the desired thermal conditions are achieved. In the “with SHMS” scenario, SHMS is assumed to be employed during curing by acquiring the internal temperature field via embedded FBG sensors, replacing conventional thermocouples. The superior accuracy of FBG measurements is expected to provide a more precise representation of the temperature distribution, potentially reducing the number of required curing cycles.

After defining the curing parameters, the next phase involves mechanical testing to evaluate the blade’s performance. This is traditionally done by applying static and fatigue loads and measuring strain with strain gauges. In the “with SHMS” scenario, the strain gauges are replaced by FBG sensors

to provide more accurate strain measurements, potentially reducing the number of required tests. The total cost of laboratory activities for developing a new composite blade is therefore divided into two components: the cost of defining the curing cycle $C_{cur\ cycle\ def}$ and the cost of conducting mechanical tests $C_{test\ lab}$ as expressed in Eq. 1.

$$C_{lab\ act} = C_{cur\ cycle\ def} + C_{test\ lab} \quad (1)$$

The process related to the laboratory activities, modeled using the IDEF0 formalism, is illustrated in Figure 1. The IDEF0 formalism is designed to map complex processes with the aim of highlighting the following elements: (i) Activities, represented by rectangular boxes; (ii) Inputs, indicated by arrows entering from the left side of each activity; (iii) Outputs, indicated by arrows exiting from the right side; (iv) Constraints, represented by arrows entering from the top; (v) Resources, represented by arrows entering from the bottom;

The cost models were developed based on the inputs and resources required for each activity within the process. A color-coding convention was adopted to distinguish between the two scenarios: activities specific to the “as-is” scenario are shown in red, those belonging to the “with SHMS” scenario are shown in green, and activities common to both scenarios are depicted in black.

Figure 1: IDEF0 model of the process of the laboratory activities necessary to develop a new composite blade

Following the IDEF0 diagram, for the scenario “as is”, the following Eq. 2 representing the cost model for the development of the curing cycle can be obtained.

$$C_{cur\ cycle\ def}^{as\ is} = (C_m + L_{tr\ wo} t_{tr\ wo} + n_{th} C_{th} + C_{energy} t_{auto} + L_{eng} t_{eng}) n_{auto}^{as\ is} + C_{acq\ sys} \frac{t_{auto} n_{auto}^{as\ is}}{t_{auto} n_{auto}^{as\ is} + t_{test} n_{test}^{as\ is}} \quad (2)$$

While, considering the scenario “with SHMS”, the following Eq. 3 can be written.

$$C_{cur\ cycle\ def}^{SHMS} = (C_m + L_{tr\ wo} t_{tr\ wo} + n_{FBG} C_{FBG} + C_{energy} t_{auto} + L_{eng} t_{eng}) n_{auto}^{SHMS} + C_{FBG\ sys} \frac{t_{auto} n_{auto}^{SHMS}}{t_{auto} n_{auto}^{SHMS} + t_{test} n_{test}^{SHMS}} \quad (3)$$

The final terms in Eq. 2 and Eq. 3 represent the cost allocation for the acquisition system in the “as-is” scenario and the interrogation system in the “with SHMS” scenario, respectively. Both equations are linearly dependent on the number of autoclave cycles required to determine the optimal curing parameters. Additionally, it can be noted that in Eq. 2, the cost associated with thermocouples is replaced in Eq. 3 by the cost of FBG sensors.

With regard to the laboratory testing activities required to complete the initial phase of blade certification, the cost models for the “as-is” and “with SHMS” scenarios are presented in Eq. 4 and Eq. 5, respectively.

$$C_{test\ lab}^{as\ is} = (C_m + L_{tr\ wo}t_{tr\ wo} + n_g C_g + C_{energy}t_{auto} + L_{eng}t_{eng})n_{test}^{as\ is} + C_{acq\ sys} \frac{t_{test}n_{test}^{as\ is}}{t_{auto}n_{auto}^{as\ is} + t_{test}n_{test}^{as\ is}} \quad (4)$$

$$C_{test\ lab}^{SHMS} = (C_m + L_{tr\ wo}t_{tr\ wo} + n_{FBG}C_{FBG} + C_{energy}t_{auto} + L_{eng}t_{eng})n_{auto}^{SHMS} + C_{FBG\ sys} \frac{t_{test}n_{test}^{SHMS}}{t_{auto}n_{auto}^{SHMS} + t_{test}n_{test}^{SHMS}} \quad (5)$$

The final term in Eq. 4 and Eq. 5 represents the cost allocation for the acquisition system in the “as-is” scenario and the interrogation system in the “with SHMS” scenario, respectively. Both equations are linearly dependent on the number of blades tested. Furthermore, it can be noted that the cost of strain gauges in Eq. 4, corresponding to the “as-is” scenario, is replaced by the cost of FBG sensors in Eq. 5, corresponding to the “with SHMS” scenario.

2.2 Middle Of Life

In accordance with step (ii) of the proposed procedure for assessing the economic impact of SHMS, the performance of the SHMS was evaluated using a finite element (FE) model, experimentally validated and representing a portion of the rotorcraft blade—specifically, the blade root. Damage was assumed to occur exclusively within the adhesive layer that bonds the central core to the surrounding antitorisional layer. Various damage sizes, ranging from 3 mm to 30 mm, were analyzed and distributed across the adhesive surface. In the FE model, damage was simulated by removing the elements enclosed within a sphere, the center of which was located on the surface of the adhesive layer. An example of a 30 mm damage scenario is shown in Figure 2a. As illustrated, two coordinate systems were employed to define damage locations: a curvilinear coordinate system along the blade’s length and a cross-sectional coordinate system. Damage was distributed at 10 equally spaced positions along the curvilinear coordinate, and for each position, four evenly spaced locations were selected across the cross section. This yielded a total of 40 damage locations. For each of these 40 locations, the following damage sizes were considered: 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, 24, and 30 mm—resulting in a total of 360 distinct damage scenarios.

The analyses served as input for training an ANN-based algorithm designed to detect the presence of damage. Strain measurements were extracted from selected elements within the FE model. Specifically, six virtual optical fiber lines were defined, each containing ten virtual FBGs, resulting in a total of 60 virtual FBGs. These were positioned inside the antitorisional layer, at a distance of 0.25 mm from the adhesive interface. To simulate realistic measurement conditions, Gaussian noise with a standard deviation of 4% was added to the sampled strain values during the training, validation, and testing phases of the ANN.

Figure 2: a) FE model of the blade root, the central core is colored green while the adhesive layer connecting the central core to the antitorisional layer is colored red; b) Receiver Operating Characteristic curve obtained for a Gaussian noise of 4%.

A pattern recognition ANN architecture was adopted, consisting of three hidden layers with ten neurons per layer. The network's output was a scalar value between 0 and 1. A blade was classified as damaged if the ANN output exceeded a predefined threshold; otherwise, it was considered undamaged. The damage detection performance of the SHMS was quantified in terms of Probability of Detection (POD) and Probability of False Alarm (PFA), as shown in Figure 2b for a 4% Gaussian noise level. Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves were generated by varying the classification threshold from 0 to 1. POD was calculated as the ratio of correctly identified damaged blades to the total number of damaged blades, while PFA represented the ratio of undamaged blades falsely classified as damaged to the total number of undamaged blades evaluated.

Step (iii) of the proposed methodology, concerning the integration of the SHMS into the rotorcraft's lifecycle, is addressed below. In both the "as-is" and "with SHMS" scenarios, helicopter downtime was considered to result in revenue loss. It was assumed that the helicopter was owned by a leasing company renting aircraft to external operators.

For the "as-is" scenario—based on practical experience in the aerospace sector—the blade was assumed to undergo two types of inspections: General Visual Inspection (GVI), performed every 50 flight hours (FH) without removing the blade from the rotor hub, and Detailed Inspection (DI), carried out using a tap hammer every 1200 FH, requiring blade removal. The annual cash flow associated with the "as-is" scenario is expressed in Equation 6.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & CF^{as\ is} \\
 & = \sum_{i=1}^{n\ travels} 2At_{depot}K_{partition} + \sum_{i=1}^{n\ blade\ mount-sched} 2Bt_{mount\ blade} \\
 & + \sum_{i=1}^{n\ blade\ mount-unsch} \frac{2}{n_b} Ct_{mount\ blade} + \sum_{i=1}^{n\ GVI} Bt_{GVI} + \sum_{i=1}^{n\ DI} Bt_{DI} + \sum_{i=1}^{n\ repairs} Ct_{repair}^{as\ is} + \sum_{i=1}^{n\ spare\ parts} c_{blade}^{as\ is}
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Where the coefficients A, B, and C were defined by the Eq. 7, Eq. 8, and Eq. 9, respectively.

$$A = (L_{pilots} + c_{fuel} + R) \tag{7}$$

$$B = (L_{tr\ wo} + RK_{partition}) \tag{8}$$

$$C = (L_{tr\ wo} + R) \tag{9}$$

Several cost elements were taken into account in Eq. 6, including travel to the maintenance

depot, blade removal from the rotor hub, performance of GVI and DI inspections, blade repair, and blade replacement. A distinction was also made between scheduled and unscheduled maintenance activities. For scheduled activities, a partition coefficient $K_{partition}$ was introduced to allocate the helicopter's revenue loss R specifically to blade-related maintenance. This reflects the fact that, during scheduled downtime, multiple maintenance tasks are typically performed concurrently across different aircraft systems. Therefore, only a portion of the total revenue loss can be attributed to rotor blade maintenance. In contrast, for unscheduled activities caused specifically by the rotor blades, this partitioning is not applicable. Since these events occur outside of the planned maintenance schedule, they do not allow for simultaneous work on other components. As a result, the full revenue loss R is attributed solely to the rotor blade issue. Consequently, unscheduled activities are significantly more costly than scheduled ones. In the "with SHMS" scenario, the GVI was assumed to be carried out identically to the "as-is" scenario. However, the SHMS was intended to progressively replace the DI. During the initial years of the blade's lifecycle, the DI interval was extended to 2400 FH, supported by additional automatic inspections enabled by the SHMS. In later years, once confidence in the SHMS's performance had grown, it was assumed that the system would fully replace DI activities, achieving a fully Condition-Based Maintenance (CBM) approach.

It is important to note that SHMS data were assumed to be retrieved at regular intervals by a ground-based operator. However, if the SHMS issued an alert and no damage was identified during the GVI, the helicopter was assumed to return to the depot for a DI using the same procedures as in the "as-is" scenario.

The annual cash flow for the "with SHMS" scenario is described by Equation 10.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & CF^{SHMS} \\
 &= \sum_{i=1}^{n \text{ travels-sched}} 2At_{depot}K_{partition} + \sum_{i=1}^{n \text{ travels-unsch}} 2At_{depot} \\
 &+ \sum_{i=1}^{n \text{ blade mount-sched}} 2Bt_{mount \text{ blade}} + \sum_{i=1}^{n \text{ blade mount-unsch}} \frac{2}{n_b} Ct_{mount \text{ blade}} + \sum_{i=1}^{n \text{ GVI-sched}} Bt_{GVI} \\
 &+ \sum_{i=1}^{n \text{ GVI-unsch}} \frac{1}{n_b} Ct_{GVI} + \sum_{i=1}^{n \text{ DI-sched}} Bt_{DI} + \sum_{i=1}^{n \text{ DI-unsch}} \frac{1}{n_b} Ct_{DI} + \sum_{i=1}^{n \text{ repairs}} Ct_{repair}^{SHMS} \\
 &+ \sum_{i=1}^{n \text{ spare parts}} c_{blade}^{SHMS}
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

It is worth noting that different costs were assumed for both the blade and the repair time compared to the "as-is" scenario. Additionally, unlike in the "as-is" case, the travel activity in the "with SHMS" scenario was considered unscheduled, as an SHMS-triggered alarm could prompt the helicopter to return to the depot for a DI.

The Net Present Value (NPV), shown in Equation 11, was selected as the performance indicator to compare the two scenarios. This metric enables the discounting of all cash flows occurring throughout the helicopter's operational lifecycle.

$$NPV = \sum_t \frac{CF(t)}{(1+r)^t} \tag{11}$$

The two scenarios—"as-is" and "with SHMS"—were compared under the same Probability of Failure (POF) for the blade, as determined through a Probabilistic Damage Tolerance Analysis [13]. According to [14], in offshore operations, a helicopter is expected to experience one main rotor impact every 1000 FH. Assuming an average usage of 500 FH per year over a 30-year lifespan, a total of 15 impacts are anticipated throughout the helicopter's lifecycle. These impacts were randomly distributed

in the lifecycle simulation. Impact energies were modeled based on the “medium energy” distribution described in [15]. Blade degradation following an impact was assumed to follow the behavior described in [16], where helicopter blades were subjected to steel sphere impacts at varying energy levels, and data were provided for residual indentation and skin-foam disbonding area. The residual strength of the blade after an impact was estimated by calculating the ratio between the cross-sectional area affected by indentation and the original cross-sectional area. A schematic representation of the blade’s strength degradation is shown in Figure 3a.

Figure 3: a) Schematic representation of the blade strength degradation function of the residual indentation; b) POD curves corresponding to the GVI, DI, obtained from [17], and SHMS, the latter calculated considering a threshold such to reach a PFA of 0.12% from the ROC curves presented in Figure 2b.

Accordingly, the following Eq. 12 was used to compute the ratio between the initial strength and the strength after an impact.

$$\text{strength ratio} = 1 - 1.5 \frac{\text{indentation area}}{\text{core area}} \quad (12)$$

A coefficient of 1.5 was introduced to account for stress concentration effects. The indentation area was calculated by approximating the shape of the cross section near the leading edge with a square root function, resulting in Eq. 13. This equation expresses the indentation area as a function of the indentation depth.

$$\text{indentation area} = 2.89 \times \text{indentation}^{1.5} \quad (13)$$

Figure 3b shows the performance of GVI, DI, and SHMS in terms of the POD as a function of damage size. It is important to note that, while damage size for DI and SHMS refers to the delamination size, for GVI it corresponds to the surface indentation. The POD curves for GVI and DI were obtained from [17], while the performance of SHMS was previously derived using the FE model of the blade root. These SHMS results were assumed to be representative of the entire blade length. Assuming the total blade length is 7.5 times longer than the portion analyzed in the FE model, the number of FBG sensors was scaled proportionally. As a result, a total of 450 FBG sensors was considered for one blade.

In the Probabilistic Damage Tolerance Analysis, the load exceedance probability per FH was calculated based on [18]. The initial blade strength ratio was set to 2, representing the ratio between the failure load and the limit load. The blade’s lifecycle was simulated on an hourly basis using a MATLAB script, averaging results across 30000 simulated scenarios. At each hour, the code checks whether it is time to perform an inspection. Accordingly, the inspection intervals for GVI, DI, and SHMS (the latter only for the “with SHMS” scenario) were defined as input parameters.

The cost model described by Eqs. 6–11 was implemented in the same script, which aggregates yearly cash flows across the lifecycle and ultimately calculates the NPV.

3 RESULTS

In this section, the final step (iv) of the procedure for assessing the economic impact of SHMS was completed. Table 1 presents selected values of the variables used in this study to evaluate the economic impact.

Variable	Value	Source
$C_{acq\ sys}$	13000 €	[19]
$C_{blade}^{as\ is}$	40000 €	DAER-lab
C_{energy}	10.6 €/h	[20]
C_{FBG}	90 €	DAER-lab
$C_{FBG\ sys}$	20000 €	[21]
c_{fuel}	272.64 €/h	[22, 23]
C_g	1 €	DAER-lab
C_m	1307 €	[20] and DAER-lab
C_{th}	10 €	[24]
$K_{partition}$	0.1	DAER-lab
L_{eng}	42 €/h	DAER-lab
L_{pilots}	48.2 €/h	[25]
$L_{tr\ wo}$	28 €/h	[26]
n_b	4	DAER-lab
n_{FBG}	450	DAER-lab
R	6560.6 €/h	[27]
r	8%	[28]
t_{auto}	8 h	DAER-lab
t_{depot}	0.5 h	DAER-lab
t_{DI}	15 h	DAER-lab
t_{eng}	0.0167 h	DAER-lab
t_{GVI}	0.652 h	DAER-lab
$t_{mount\ blade}$	0.5 h	DAER-lab
$t_{repair}^{as\ is}$	8 h	DAER-lab
$t_{tr\ wo}$	25 h	DAER-lab

Table 1: values and sources of the variables assumed in this study.

3.1 Beginning Of Life

The results related to the BOL analysis highlighted the presence of break-even points, beyond which one of the two scenarios becomes more economically advantageous than the other.

In terms of curing cycle development, it was found that if the number of cycles required to identify the optimal curing parameters is significantly reduced—thanks to the improved temperature field quality provided by FBG sensors—an economic benefit can be achieved. In this case, the “with SHMS” scenario becomes more favourable. For example, as shown in Figure 4a, if the number of curing cycles decreases from 26 in the “as is” scenario to fewer than 19 when using 10 FBG sensors (the “with SHMS” scenario), then the “with SHMS” scenario becomes more economically viable.

A similar trend was observed in relation to the laboratory tests required during the initial stage of blade certification. Here too, break-even points exist beyond which one scenario becomes more advantageous than the other. Specifically, if the number of tested blades can be sufficiently reduced—thanks to the improved strain field data from FBG sensors—an economic benefit is achieved under the “with SHMS” scenario. For instance, as shown in Figure 4b, if the number of tested blades decreases

from 22 in the “as is” scenario to fewer than 18 in the “with SHMS” scenario using 10 FBG sensors, the latter becomes the more cost-effective option.

Figure 4: a) Cost of the curing cycle development versus the number of curing cycles performed, with sensitivity analysis on the number of FBG sensors embedded in the blade; b) Cost of laboratory tests versus the number of laboratory tests, with sensitivity analysis on the the number of FBG sensors embedded in the blade.

3.2 Middle Of Life

The results related to the MOL phase indicated that, in the “with SHMS” scenario, it was possible to extend the DI interval up to 2400 FH, provided that automatic inspections using SHMS were performed every 1070 FH. This extension maintained the same POF for the blade as in the original scenario. For this reason, the comparison between the two scenarios was conducted assuming an automatic inspection interval of 1070 FH for the SHMS. As shown in Figure 5, this condition is represented by the green vertical dashed line. Comparing the two scenarios at this inspection interval reveals a negative economic impact associated with the SHMS over the helicopter’s lifecycle.

Figure 5: a) POF and NPV function of the inspection interval of the SHMS, with sensitivity analysis on the repairing time of the sensorized blade; b) POF and NPV function of the inspection interval of the SHMS, with sensitivity analysis on the number of FBG sensors charged to the customer.

Specifically, as illustrated in Figure 5, points A and B correspond to the “as is” and “with SHMS” scenarios, respectively. The NPV for the “as is” scenario is €1.89 × 10⁵, while the NPV for the “with SHMS” scenario is €2.726 × 10⁵. This indicates that maintenance in the “with SHMS” scenario is more expensive than in the “as is” scenario.

One of the main reasons for this outcome is the high number of unscheduled maintenance activities triggered by SHMS alarms, which makes it difficult to coordinate maintenance operations and consequently increases helicopter downtime. In fact, an analysis of the NPV breakdown shows that the use of SHMS led to a reduction in the effort required for DI, decreasing from 22% in the “as is”

scenario to 6% in the “with SHMS” scenario. However, this saving was offset by increased costs related to spare parts and repair operations.

It is also worth noting the findings from the sensitivity analyses shown in Figures 5a and 5b. These results indicate that even when assuming the same repair time of 8 hours for both standard and sensorized blades, the “as is” scenario remains the more cost-effective option. Furthermore, even under the assumption that the cost of the FBG sensors is not passed on to the customer—as illustrated in Figure 5b—the “as is” scenario continues to be the more economically favourable choice.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the economic impact of an FBG-based SHMS was investigated from two perspectives: BOL and MOL. The assessment followed the LCC methodology, which involves comparing different alternatives. In this study, two scenarios were evaluated: the current baseline scenario (“as is”) and the scenario incorporating SHMS (“with SHMS”).

Several key conclusions can be drawn from the analysis. First, a methodology to assess the economic impact of SHMS was developed and applied to the case of a rotorcraft composite blade. Although tailored to this specific application, the methodology can be generalized and adapted to other composite structural components. Second, at the BOL stage, SHMS implementation was shown to have a positive economic impact when a sufficient number of autoclave cycles are saved during the definition of curing parameters. Third, for the MOL stage, the use of SHMS on the composite rotorcraft blade resulted in a negative economic outcome. The savings achieved through automated scheduled inspections using SHMS were offset by the higher costs of spare parts and increased complexity of repair operations. To make SHMS economically viable, they should be applied to structural components that are difficult to access during maintenance. In such cases, the full potential of SHMS to reduce maintenance burden and downtime can be more effectively leveraged.

Future work should aim to quantify the actual reduction in the number of curing cycles and laboratory tests, made possible by the improved quality of temperature and strain field measurements obtained through FBG sensors.

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